

PPS-40

April 22-25, 2025
Auckland, New Zealand

40th International Conference of the Polymer Processing Society

Abstract book

April 22 – 25, 2025
University of Auckland
Auckland, New Zealand

UNIVERSITY OF
AUCKLAND
Waipapa Taumata Rau
NEW ZEALAND

CENTRE FOR ADVANCED MATERIALS
MANUFACTURING & DESIGN

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Organising Committee

Conference Chair	Johan Verbeek, University of Auckland
Program	Jesna Ashraf, University of Auckland Nam Kim, University of Auckland Chanelle Gavin, University of Waikato Tom Allen, University of Auckland
Volunteers	Maedeh Amirpour, University of Auckland
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Poster session	Erin Leitao, University of Auckland Jadranka Travas-Sejdic, University of Auckland
General organisation	Mark Battley, University of Auckland Simon Bickerton, University of Auckland Krishnan Jayaraman, University of Auckland Mark Steiger, Canterbury University

Welcoming Remarks

Dear Colleagues and Friends,

It is with great pleasure that I welcome you to the 40th International Conference of the Polymer Processing Society, held in the beautiful city of Auckland, New Zealand, from the 21st to the 25th of April 2025. This year marks a momentous milestone as we gather to explore the theme “The next 40 years of polymer processing.”

Hosted by the Centre of Advanced Materials Manufacturing and Design, in the Faculty of Engineering and Design at the University of Auckland, this conference continues to be one of the most prestigious meetings in our field. We remember our recent conferences in Colombia (2024) and Switzerland (2023), and we eagerly anticipate our upcoming 2026 conference in Italy.

This year, we are thrilled to host 20 different symposia alongside a special symposium on “Commercialization and Challenges in Shaping a Circular Economy for Plastics.” The response has been overwhelming, with 325 contributions encompassing 6 plenary talks, 42 keynote talks, 210 oral presentations, and 67 poster presentations, organized into 6 parallel streams over 4 days. We are proud to see representation from 34 countries, truly making this a truly global event.

Attending an international conference such as this is invaluable. It offers a unique opportunity to expand our knowledge, share innovative research, and hear about the latest advancements in polymer processing. Equally important, it provides a platform to build lasting networks and forge meaningful relationships with peers from around the world. These connections often lead to fruitful collaborations and friendships that transcend borders and propel our field forward.

Auckland, our host city, is a vibrant international destination renowned for its stunning landscapes, rich cultural heritage, and warm hospitality. As the largest city in New Zealand, Auckland offers a perfect blend of urban sophistication and natural beauty. Attendees will have the chance to explore its picturesque harbours, lush parks, and dynamic arts scene. With its diverse culinary offerings and welcoming atmosphere, Auckland promises an unforgettable experience for all.

In conclusion, I urge you to take full advantage of this conference, engage actively in discussions, and immerse yourself in the wealth of knowledge and expertise gathered here. Together, let us pave the way for the next 40 years of pioneering advancements in polymer processing. Once again, I extend my heartfelt welcome to each of you. May this conference be a testament to our collective dedication, innovation, and collaboration.

Warm regards,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Johan Verbeek', written in a cursive style.

Johan Verbeek
Conference Chair of PPS-40

Polymer Processing Society

The Polymer Processing Society was founded in March 1985 at the University of Akron, Ohio, USA; the intent was to provide a mechanism and format for interaction and presentation of research results in the international polymer processing community; the goals are to foster scientific understanding and technical innovation in polymer processing by providing a discussion forum for the worldwide community of Engineers and Scientist in the field. The thematic range encompasses all formulations, conversion and shaping operations applied to polymeric systems in the transformation from their monomeric forms to commercial products. Membership for the PPS is open to all researchers in the field and to all persons who feel the activities of the society advance their professional development.

PPS website: www.tpps.org

Executive and International Representatives

Executive Committee

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Volker Altstädt, **President elect** (Germany)
Anup K. Ghosh, **Past-President** (India)
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Tim Osswald, **Treasurer** (USA)

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Paula Moldenaers, **Member-at-Large** (Belgium)
Hiroshi Ito, **Member-at-Large** (Japan)

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John Vlachopoulos, **Membership Chair** (Canada)

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Ana Isabel Ares Pernas (Spain)
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Fardin Khabaz (United States)
Pablo Raimonda (Uruguay)
Phan Trung Nghia (Vietnam)

International Scientific Committee

Additive manufacturing

Anderson, Patrick David	Netherlands
Liu, Shih-Jung	Taiwan
Roman, Allen Jonathan	USA
Sun, Luyi	USA
Xia, Hesheng	China
Yourdkhani, Mostafa	USA

Biomedical applications

Didar, Tohid	Canada
Perret, Edith	Switzerland
Schauer, Caroline	USA
Turng, Lih-Sheng	USA

Biopolymers

Averous, Luc	France
Chan, Clement	Australia
Halley, Pete	Australia
Hong, Joung Sook	Korea
Machado, Ana	Portugal
Raquez, Jean-Marie	Belgium

Circular Economy for Plastics and Recycling

Dhooge, Dagmar	Belgium
Fiorio, Rudinei	Netherlands
Kenig, Samuel	Israel
Manas-Zloczower, Ica	USA
Puch, Florian	Germany
Ragaert, Kim	Netherlands
Raimonda, Pablo Alberto	Uruguay
Vlachopoulos, John	Canada

Degradation, biodegradation and composting

Ray, Suprakas Sinha	South Africa
Saha, Petr	Czech

Extrusion

Lee, Patrick	Canada
Rauwendaal, Chris	USA

Fibres and Films

Ajji, Abdellah Ajji	Canada
Kikutani, Takeshi	Japan
Kornev, Konstantin	USA
Ozden, Yenigun Elif	United Kingdom

Foams and Membranes

Altstädt, Volker	Germany
Foudazi, Reza	USA
Nofar, M. Reza	Turkey
Taki, Kentaro	Japan

Functional Additives and Reactive Processing

Jana, Sadhan	USA
Sobkowicz, Meg	USA

Industry 4.0 and AI

Hrymak, Andrew	Canada
Zhang, Jie	United Kingdom

Injection moulding

Candal, Maria Virginia	Spain
Coates, Phil	United Kingdom
Cruz, Camilo	Germany
Kuehnert, Ines	Germany
Pantani, Roberto	Italy
Van Bael, Albert	Belgium

Mixing and Compounding

Carmen, Rosales	Venezuela
Wiessner, Sven	Germany

Modelling and Simulation

Albuquerque, Rodrigo	Germany
Altan, M. Cengiz	USA
Costa, Franco	Australia
Gooneie, Ali	Netherlands
Mitsoulis, Evan	Greece

Morphology and Structural Development

Cakmak, Miko	USA
Yamaguchi, Masayuki	Japan

Nanotechnology

McNally, Tony	United Kingdom
Subdararaj, Uttandaraman	Canada

Polymer Blends and Alloys

Naskar, Kinsuk	India
Ougizawa, Toshiaki	Japan

Polymer Composites

Acosta-Sullcahuamán, Julio	Peru
Arnal, Maria	Venezuela
Bernal, Celina	Argentina
Dagreou, Sylvie	France
De Paoli, Marco Aurelio	Brazil
Kenny, Jose	Italy
Leon-Becerra, Juan	Colombia
Menceloglu, Yusuf	Turkey
Mueller, Michael Thomas	Germany
Zhang, Jinwen	USA

Polymerisation and synthesis

Jin, Jianyong	New Zealand
Rueda-Sanchez, Juan Carlos	Peru

Rheology and characterisation

Frontini, Patricia	Argentina
Grizzuti, Nino	Italy

Rubbers and elastomers

Alexandrova, Larissa	Mexico
Thomas, Sabu	India

Awards

Morand Lambla Award

The Morand Lambla Award honors and outstanding young researcher in the field of polymer processing and related fields such as polymer chemistry, polymer characterisation and processing of polymeric-based products at an international level. The award aims at stimulating and recognizing originality, high achievement, and potential for continuing creativity among young researchers in the science and technology of preparing polymers and polymeric products.

Candidates can come from any part of the world and need not be PPS member. Further, they may currently be working in industrial, governmental, or academic positions. To be eligible, nominees must not yet reach their 45th birthday by Dec 31 of the current year. The nomination forms are available on the PPS website. The award consists of a recognition plaque and a \$3000 check.

Award recipient 2025 **Prof. Mohammad Arjmand**

Dr. Mohammad Arjmand is recognized as a leading (and award-winning) researcher in the fields of nanotechnology and polymer engineering. His impact can be seen through his roles at the University of British Columbia (UBC) as a faculty member, a Canada Research Chair in Advanced Materials and Polymer Engineering, an Inductee of the Royal Society of Canada, and the Lead of the Plastic Recycling Research Cluster. Dr. Arjmand's research area is focused on the synthesis of multifunctional nanomaterials and the development of their polymer nanocomposites and assemblies. During his academic career, Dr. Arjmand has been honored with numerous awards and recognitions, such as UBC Okanagan Researcher of Year (2025), Charles A. McDowell Award for Excellence in Research at UBC (2025), Morand Lambla Award from Polymer Processing Society (2025), Elected Member of College of Royal Society of Canada (2024), Canadian Society of Chemical Engineering Lectureship Award (2024), Emerging Materials Chemistry Investigator from Canadian Society of Chemistry (2024), Journal of Nanoscale Emerging Investigator (2024), Journal of Materials Chemistry Emerging Investigator (2023), Killam Faculty Research Prize from UBC (2023), Canadian Society of Chemical Engineering (CSE) Innovation Award (2022), Polymeric Materials: Science and Engineering (PMSE) Young Investigator Award from American Chemical Society (2022), Polymer Processing Society (PPS) Early Career Award (2021), and Canada Research Chair in Advanced Materials and Polymer Engineering (2019).

PPS Early Career Award

The 2025 PPS Early Career Award honors outstanding young researchers in polymer processing who received a Ph.D. degree (or equivalent) in the last 8 years. It aims to recognize and stimulate originality and potential for continuing creativity in the science and technology of polymer processing-related areas. The nominees may include tenured/tenure-track faculty members, post-doctoral researchers, and researchers working in industry or national laboratories. The award consists of a framed certificate and a cash prize of US\$2000.

Award recipient 2025

Prof. Zhe Qiang (University of Southern Mississippi)

Dr. Zhe Qiang is the SSCT Endowed Chair and Associate Professor of Polymer Science and Engineering at the University of Southern Mississippi (USM). He earned his M.S. and Ph.D. degrees in Polymer Engineering from the University of Akron and subsequently completed a postdoctoral fellowship at Northwestern University. Dr. Qiang's research

group focuses on the materials and manufacturing science of polymers and their derived functional materials, with an emphasis on sustainable development for the environment and society, including industrial decarbonization and waste recycling. Since beginning his independent career in 2019, Dr. Qiang has received many awards and honors, including being named to *Forbes* 30 Under 30 in Science (2022), the ACS PMSE Early Career Investigator (2023), SAMPE Young Professional of the Year (2023), NSF CAREER Award recipient (2023), AIChE 35 Under 35 (2023), RCSA Scialog Fellow, IUPAC Young Observer (2025), and the PPS Early Career Award (2025).

Award recipient 2024

Dr. Gace Gu (University of California, Berkeley)

Dr. Grace X. Gu is an Assistant Professor of Mechanical Engineering at the University of California, Berkeley. She received her PhD and MS in Mechanical Engineering from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and her BS in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Michigan, Ann Arbor. Her research focuses on creating new materials with superior

properties for mechanical, biological, and energy applications using multiphysics modeling and artificial intelligence, as well as developing intelligent polymer additive manufacturing processes to realize complex material designs. Recently, her group is working on in-situ monitoring and process optimization for additive manufacturing of sustainable materials such as biopolymers, recycled materials, and calcium carbonate-based composites, aiming to enhance their quality and reliability. Her work has been highlighted in various media outlets such as *Popular Science*, *Smithsonian* magazine, and *3D-Printing Industry*. She is the recipient of several awards, including the PPS Early Career Award, Sloan Research Fellowship, TMS Early Career Faculty Fellow Award, PMSE ACS Young Investigator Award, ARO Early Career Program Award, LLNL Early Career UC Faculty Initiative Award, DARPA Young Faculty Award, *Materials Today* Rising Star Award, ASME Orr Early Career Award, ONR Young Investigator Award, and 3M Non-Tenured Faculty Award. She has given dozens of invited lectures and seminars, including TEDxBerkeley. Gu has co-organized symposiums at various conferences and serves on the advisory boards of several journals, including *Composites Science and Technology*, *MRS Communications*, and *Materials Horizons*.

Program overview

MONDAY 21 APRIL						
12noon	Registration					
1:30-2:30pm	Executive meeting - Decima Glenn Room (260-310)					
2:30-3:00pm	Afternoon tea					
3-4:30pm	Executive meeting and International representatives - Decima Glenn Room (260-310)					
TUESDAY 22 APRIL						
8am	Registration					
9am-9:30am	Conference opening - Fisher & Paykel Auditorium					
9:30-10:20am	Plenary 1					
10:20-10:50am	Morning tea					
10:50am-12:10pm Session 1.1	Polymer Composites Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Circular Economy for Plastics and Recycling OGGB 3, 260-092	Modelling and Simulation OGGB 4, 260-073	Additive manufacturing OGGB 5, 260-051	Biopolymers Case Room 2, 260-057	Morphology and Structural Development Case Room 3, 260-055
12:10-1pm	Lunch					
1pm-1:50pm	Plenary 2 - Fisher & Paykel Auditorium					
2-3:30pm Session 1.2	Polymer Composites Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Circular Economy for Plastics and Recycling OGGB 3, 260-092	Modelling and Simulation OGGB 4, 260-073	Additive manufacturing OGGB 5, 260-051	Foams and Membranes Case Room 2, 260-057	Morphology and Structural Development Case Room 3, 260-055
3:30-4pm	Afternoon tea					
4-5:30pm Session 1.3	Polymer Composites Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Circular Economy for Plastics and Recycling OGGB 3, 260-092	Fibres and Films OGGB 4, 260-073	Additive manufacturing OGGB 5, 260-051	Foams and Membranes Case Room 2, 260-057	Injection moulding Case Room 3, 260-055
6-8pm	Welcome function and Poster Session					
WEDNESDAY 23 APRIL						
8:30-9:20am	Plenary 3 - Fisher & Paykel Auditorium					
9:20-10:30am Session 2.1	Special Symposia Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Nanotechnology OGGB 3, 260-092	Industry 4.0 and AI OGGB 4, 260-073	Rubbers and elastomers OGGB 5, 260-051	Biopolymers Case Room 2, 260-057	Rheology and characterisation Case Room 3, 260-055
10:30-11am	Morning tea					
11am-12:30pm Session 2.2	Polymer Composites Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Circular Economy for Plastics and Recycling OGGB 3, 260-092	Polymerisation and synthesis OGGB 4, 260-073	Extrusion OGGB 5, 260-051	Polymer Blends and Alloys Case Room 2, 260-057	Mixing and Compounding Case Room 3, 260-055
12:30-1:30pm	Lunch Editorial board meeting - Case Room 2, 260-057					
1:30-2:20pm	Plenary 4 - Fisher & Paykel Auditorium					
2:20-3:40pm Session 2.3	Extrusion Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Circular Economy for Plastics and Recycling OGGB 3, 260-092	Modelling and Simulation OGGB 4, 260-073	Additive manufacturing OGGB 5, 260-051	Biopolymers Case Room 2, 260-057	Injection moulding Case Room 3, 260-055
3:40-4:10pm	Afternoon tea					
4:10-5:20pm Session 2.4	Polymer Composites Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Nanotechnology OGGB 3, 260-092	Modelling and Simulation OGGB 4, 260-073	Rubbers and elastomers OGGB 5, 260-051	Biopolymers Case Room 2, 260-057	Biomedical applications Case Room 3, 260-055

THURSDAY 24 APRIL						
8:30-9:20am	Plenary 5 - Fisher & Paykel Auditorium					
9:20-10:20am Session 3.1	Industry 4.0 and AI Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Circular Economy for Plastics and Recycling OGGB 3, 260-092	Functional Additives and Reactive Processing OGGB 4, 260-073	Additive manufacturing OGGB 5, 260-051	Rubbers and elastomers Case Room 2, 260-057	Biomedical applications Case Room 3, 260-055
10:20-11am	Morning tea					
11am-12:30pm Session 3.2	Polymer Composites Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Fibres and Films OGGB 3, 260-092	Degradation, biodegradation and composting OGGB 4, 260-073	Injection moulding OGGB 5, 260-051	Foams and Membranes Case Room 2, 260-057	Biomedical applications Case Room 3, 260-055
12:30-1:30pm	Lunch Business Lunch - OGGB3, 260-092					
1:30-2:20pm	Keynote: Early Career Winner 2024 - Fisher & Paykel Auditorium					
2:20-3:50pm Session 3.3	Polymer Composites Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Circular Economy for Plastics and Recycling OGGB 3, 260-092	Modelling and Simulation OGGB 4, 260-073	Injection moulding OGGB 5, 260-051	Biopolymers Case Room 2, 260-057	Degradation, biodegradation and composting Case Room 3, 260-055
3:50-4:20pm	Afternoon tea					
4:20-5pm Session 3.4	Industry 4.0 and AI Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Circular Economy for Plastics and Recycling OGGB 3, 260-092	Polymerisation and synthesis OGGB 4, 260-073	Morphology and Structural Development OGGB 5, 260-051	Rheology and characterisation Case Room 2, 260-057	Biomedical applications Case Room 3, 260-055
7-11pm	Conference Banquet at the Auckland Museum (Buses depart from Owen G Glen Building from 5:15pm)					
FRIDAY 25 APRIL						
1-2:30pm	Plenary 7: Lamda Award Winner 2025 & Keynote: Early Career Winner 2025 Fisher & Paykel Auditorium					
2:30-3pm	Afternoon tea					
3-4:30pm Session 4.1	Polymer Composites Lecture Theatre, 260-098	Functional Additives and Reactive Processing OGGB 3, 260-092	Modelling and Simulation OGGB 4, 260-073	Morphology and Structural Development OGGB 5, 260-051	Polymer Blends and Alloys Case Room 2, 260-057	Fibres and Films Case Room 3, 260-055
4:45-5:15pm	Conference Closing - Fisher & Paykel Auditorium					

Colour coding by topic

ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING
BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS
BIOPOLYMERS
CIRCULAR ECONOMY FOR PLASTICS AND RECYCLING
DEGRADATION, BIODEGRADATION AND COMPOSTING
EXTRUSION
FIBRES AND FILMS
INDUSTRY 4.0 AND AI
FOAMS AND MEMBRANES
FUNCTIONAL ADDITIVES AND REACTIVE PROCESSING

INJECTION MOULDING
MIXING AND COMPOUNDING
MODELLING AND SIMULATION
MORPHOLOGY AND STRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT
NANOTECHNOLOGY
POLYMER BLENDS AND ALLOYS
POLYMER COMPOSITES
POLYMERISATION AND SYNTHESIS
RHEOLOGY AND CHARACTERISATION
RUBBERS AND ELASTOMERS

Abstracts – Posters

Abstracts of PPS - 40

Posters

Poster: Modelling and Simulation

Paper ID: S33-339

Designing extrusion screws using artificial intelligence

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Abstract

The interest in the issues of artificial intelligence of many different centers around the world has brought specific results that have already found practical and widespread applications. "Artificial intelligence" has become increasingly popular and more frequently used in recent years. The rapid development of electronics and computer science is conducive to the development of this field of science. "Intelligent machines" are needed by humans to create and discover new relationships, and artificial intelligence has significantly influenced various areas of technology and, above all, has achieved great implementation success in areas where a large amount of data is available. It is also increasingly used in the processing of polymer materials. The designs of screws of plasticizing systems of extruders are largely proprietary and there is very little specific information available in the literature. Our team generated a set of many extrusion screw designs using computer simulation software for the extrusion process, including the transport of solids, melting and pumping of the melt. The parameters and results obtained were entered into four machine learning algorithms. The performance of the four algorithms was evaluated by comparing the predictions of each algorithm with the corresponding simulation results. For three of the algorithms, we obtained satisfactory performance, and the best one was additionally evaluated using a previously "unseen" dataset consisting of two screws with defined diameters. It is argued that the same ML methodologies can be applied to datasets of existing real-world screw designs. Our conclusion is that the data-driven methodology presented in this paper can be used in the design of extruder screws, leveraging knowledge gained from the development of existing designs.

List of All Authors

(Name, Abstract #)

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Ainali Nina María (370)
Akbarinejad Alireza (325)
Albuquerque Rodrigo (257)
Allen Tom David (290, 210)
Alsuhaibani Faisal (318)
Alves Franciso (393)
Amini Majed(506)
Amiri Zahra (447)
Amirian Amirali (359)
Amirpour Maedeh (359, 326)
An Yunpeng (101)
Anderson Patrick (113)
Anderson Patrick D. (133)
Ares-Pernas Ana Isabel (300)
Arjmand Mohammad(506)
Artemeva Marina (43)
Ashraf Jesna (450, 210, 323)
Auhl Dietmar Werner (179)
Avallone Pietro Renato (144)
Avella Angelica (224)
Avshalomov Rachel (132)
Aw Kean (78)
Azhar Kashif (431)
Bae Jong Hyuk (316, 400)
Bae Jong-Hyuk (376)
Bagal Rohit (394, 278)
Bai Bing Shi (270)
Bai Shibing (168)
Baierl Zachary (200)
Bandyopadhyay Jayita (21)
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